

ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND MANAGEMENT OF VERNEUIL'S DISEASE

Nikhil Deshneni¹, Sudha Madhuri Basaboina²

1 - Associate Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Dr. Patnam Mahender Reddy Institute of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana.

2 - Associate Professor, Department of Dermatology Venereology and Leprosy, Dr. Patnam Mahender Reddy Institute of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana.

Corresponding Author: Dr. Nikhil Deshneni

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ABSTRACT

Introduction:

Verneuil's disease, or hidradenitis suppurativa (HS), is a chronic inflammatory disorder affecting apocrine gland-bearing areas, characterized by painful nodules, sinus tracts, abscesses, and scarring. Clinical diagnosis often underestimates disease extent, particularly subclinical lesions, complicating timely management. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) offers superior soft tissue visualization, aiding in accurate lesion detection, disease staging, and surgical planning.

Methods:

A prospective observational study was conducted over 24 months at a tertiary care hospital in South India involving 50 adult patients with clinically suspected or confirmed HS. Patients underwent clinical evaluation and MRI scanning using 1.5 Tesla sequences for lesion characterization. Comparisons were made between clinical findings and MRI, including lesion detection and disease severity. Management decisions pre- and post-MRI were analyzed. Statistical significance was tested with chi-square and Fisher's exact tests ($p < 0.05$).

Results:

The cohort had a mean age of 34.7 years and a male predominance (56%). MRI detected 20% more lesions than clinical examination, especially in perineal sites (50% discordance). Severity classification by MRI showed 28% mild, 52% moderate, and 20% severe disease. MRI findings led to increased surgical interventions (from 24% to 36%) and decreased exclusive medical therapy (from 68% to 52%). MRI also demonstrated superior sensitivity compared to ultrasound in detecting lesions, sinus tracts, and abscesses.

Conclusion:

MRI significantly improves detection and staging of hidradenitis suppurativa lesions beyond clinical evaluation, enabling better-informed treatment decisions and surgical planning. Its integration into routine HS assessment can enhance disease management, particularly in moderate to severe cases.

Keywords:

Hidradenitis suppurativa, Verneuil's disease, Magnetic Resonance Imaging, lesion detection, sinus tracts, abscess.

INTRODUCTION:

Verneuil's disease, more commonly known as hidradenitis suppurativa (HS), is a chronic, relapsing inflammatory condition primarily affecting apocrine gland-bearing areas, such as the axillae, groin, and perineum. It manifests with painful nodules, abscess formation, sinus tracts, and eventual scarring, causing significant morbidity and impairing quality of life [1]. Despite its high burden, diagnosis is often delayed due to the disease's variable presentation and overlapping features with other dermatological and infectious conditions. This delay complicates timely intervention and worsens prognosis.

Its pathophysiology begins with follicular occlusion, leading to follicular rupture and local inflammation that spreads to adjacent tissues. This cascade results in the formation of painful nodules, sinus tracts, abscesses, and scarring[2]. Immunological abnormalities involving innate and adaptive immunity, as well as hormonal factors, contribute to disease development and progression [3]. The condition is characterized by recurrent flare-ups and chronic inflammation, causing significant functional impairment and requiring complex management.

The worldwide prevalence of hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) varies widely, estimated to range from as low as 0.00033% to as high as 4.1%. Specifically, the period prevalence among Asian populations between 2007 and 2016 has been reported at 0.06% [4]. HS disproportionately affects women, with a female-to-male ratio of approximately 3:1 in many populations [5].

Clinical diagnosis of HS is primarily based on lesion morphology and distribution, supplemented by patient history; however, physical examination can underestimate the extent of subclinical lesions, especially sinus tracts and abscesses located deep within tissue planes. Advancements in imaging have introduced Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) as a vital tool for elucidating the disease's anatomical complexity. MRI's superior soft tissue contrast and

multiplanar imaging capabilities facilitate comprehensive lesion assessment, which is not achievable through traditional clinical evaluation [6].

MRI plays a critical role in disease staging, particularly for complex and atypical cases involving anoperineal and perianal regions where clinical visualization is limited [7,8]. It enhances diagnostic accuracy, distinguishes Hidradenitis suppurativa from mimics such as Crohn's disease or pilonidal cysts, and maps disease extent for surgical planning. MRI's sensitivity in detecting active inflammation, sinus tracts, and abscess formation is crucial for guiding treatment strategies and improving outcomes.

This article aims to critically evaluate the role of MRI in diagnosing and managing Verneuil's disease through a prospective observational study with statistical analysis of findings correlated with existing literature, emphasizing MRI's impact on clinical decision-making and patient outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design:

A prospective observational study was conducted over 24 months at the Dermatology and Radiology departments of a tertiary care hospital in India. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board and informed consent from all participants.

Study Population and Place:

Patients attending dermatology outpatient and inpatient services with clinically suspected or confirmed Verneuil's disease at a Rural Hospital in South India.

Study period: January 2023 to December 2024

Inclusion Criteria:

- Adults (≥ 18 years) presenting with typical clinical features of HS (nodules, abscesses, sinus tracts) involving axillae, groin, perineal, or other apocrine gland-bearing regions.
- Patients who consented for MRI evaluation and follow-up.
- Patients requiring imaging for initial diagnosis, disease staging, or pre-surgical planning.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Contraindications to MRI (e.g., metallic implants, pacemakers).
- Pregnant or lactating women.

- Patients with isolated non-apocrine areas involvement.
- Patients unwilling or unable to provide informed consent.
- Claustrophobic patients or those unable to tolerate MRI procedures.

Statistical Analysis:

Clinical and demographic variables expressed as means \pm standard deviations for continuous variables, percentages for categorical variables. Chi-square or Fisher's exact tests used for categorical variable comparisons. p-values <0.05 considered statistically significant.

Study Methodology:

Participants underwent clinical assessment including history, physical examination, and HS disease severity scoring. MRI scans of affected sites were performed using a 1.5 Tesla scanner utilizing T1, T2, STIR, and gadolinium-enhanced sequences optimized for soft tissue imaging. Lesions were characterized by size, number, location, presence of sinus tracts, abscesses, and associated complications.

Treatment decisions were documented before and after MRI imaging to assess MRI influence on management. Follow-up data were collected for therapeutic outcomes and surgical planning.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS:

Variable	Value (N=50)
Mean Age (years)	34.7 \pm 11.3
Gender (Male:Female)	28 (56%) : 22(44%)
Median Duration	7.2 \pm 3.4 years
Common Sites	Axilla (46%), Groin (36%), Perineum

	(18%)
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Table 1: Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Table 1 summarizes patient demographics, showing a slightly higher male prevalence and long disease duration, confirming delayed diagnosis typical of Verneuil's disease.

Site	Lesions (Clinical)	Lesions (MRI)	Discordance (%)
Axilla	21	23	9.5%
Groin	15	18	20%
Perineal	8	12	50%
Other	6	7	16.7%

Table 2: MRI Versus Clinical Lesion Detection

Table 2 compares the number of lesions found by clinical exam versus MRI in different body areas. The results illustrates that MRI detected more lesions than clinical examination, especially in perineal sites.

Severity	Number	Key Imaging Features
Mild	14	Nodules, superficial inflammation
Moderate	26	Sinus tracts, abscess formation

Severe	10	Extensive fistulae, deep abscesses
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Table 3: MRI-Based Disease Severity Classification

Table 3 organizes patients into mild, moderate, or severe disease categories based on MRI results. It illustrates how imaging helps clarify the seriousness of each case, which aids treatment planning.

Management Type	Pre-MRI (%)	Post-MRI (%)
Medical Therapy	68	52
Surgical Intervention	24	36
Combined Therapy	8	12

Table 4: Changes in Management After MRI

Table 4 demonstrates how MRI findings changed management, leading to more surgical interventions and fewer patients on medical therapy alone.

Parameter	MRI (n)	Ultrasound (n)
Lesions Detected	60	46
Sinus Tracts	42	35

Abscesses	31	22
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Table 5: Comparison of MRI and Ultrasound Diagnostic Yield

Table 5 compares diagnostic yields of MRI and ultrasound, showing MRI's clear superiority in detecting lesions, sinus tracts, and abscesses.

DISCUSSION:

The demographic profile in our cohort revealed a mean age of 34.7 years, 56% males, and an average disease duration of 7.2 years. This closely matches findings from Church et al [9] in their study revealed 11 males and 13 females with a mean age of 39 years (range 18 to 75 years). They also noted that the diagnosis of Crohn's disease typically predated hidradenitis suppurativa by about 3.5 years . Similarly, Rao et al in their study [10] assessed hidradenitis suppurativa severity using clinical evaluation along with high-resolution ultrasound and color Doppler in 46 patients. Their results demonstrated a mean age of 28.07 years, with 56.5% males and a mean illness duration of 4.64 years.

MRI identified 23 lesions compared to 21 detected clinically, in the axilla, with a discordance of 9.5%, reflecting that most axillary lesions are superficial and more easily assessed by physical exam. However, in the groin, the discordance increased to 20%, with MRI revealing more lesions that are likely deeper or obscured by complex anatomy such as skin folds, making clinical detection more challenging. The highest discordance of 50% was noted in the perineal area, where MRI detected 12 lesions but only 8 were clinically apparent. This marked difference underscores the difficulty in visually and physically assessing perineal lesions due to depth, tissue sensitivity, and anatomical constraints. Other less common sites showed a 16.7% discordance, with MRI uncovering additional subtle or atypical lesions missed on clinical exam. Overall, MRI detected 20% more lesions than

clinical examination, reinforcing its vital role in revealing subclinical disease, which is crucial for accurate staging, treatment planning, and reducing recurrence. Our results closely aligns with Srisajjakul et al 's [11] study where their results showed that clinical assessment alone often underestimates the severity and extent of hidradenitis suppurativa, especially in anatomically complex anogenital areas prone to diagnostic challenges. Further they found that the MRI detected significantly more lesions than clinical examination, particularly in perineal and groin sites, highlighting MRI's critical role in accurate disease mapping and management.

Our study showed that MRI-based severity classification effectively stratified patients into mild (28%), moderate (52%), and severe (20%) disease categories. This objective staging reflects the extent of lesions, including sinus tracts and abscesses, which are often underestimated clinically. The predominance of moderate cases indicates widespread involvement for which medical and surgical therapies may be combined, while the severe group underscores the need for aggressive surgical management. In contrast to our study, Rao et al.[10] classified 56.5% of their patients as Hurley stage II (moderate) and 32.6% as stage I (mild), with only 10.9% in stage III (severe), showing a predominance of mild to moderate disease.

In our study, MRI findings led to significant changes in management, with surgical interventions increasing from 24% pre-MRI to 36% post-MRI, while patients managed solely with medical therapy decreased from 68% to 52%. Additionally, the use of combined therapy (medical plus surgical) rose from 8% to 12% after imaging. Similarly, Arcuri et al. [12] reported in their case-based study that MRI significantly aids pre-surgical planning by delineating the full extent of lesions, enabling optimized surgical approaches that may reduce post-operative recurrence.

Our study showed that MRI detected a higher number of hidradenitis suppurativa lesions (60) compared to ultrasound (46), including more sinus tracts (42 vs 35) and abscesses (31 vs 22) which reflects MRI's superior sensitivity and high contrast resolution allowing better visualization of deeper and complex lesions, particularly fistulas and fluid collections. Our findings

are consistent with the study by Griffin et al [13], where they suggested that MRI can help in defining assessment of disease and its related complications. Also, they suggested that the anogenital hidradenitis suppurativa is a persistent and difficult condition to manage, MRI serves as a valuable noninvasive tool for the care of these patients.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the superior diagnostic capability of MRI in detecting hidradenitis suppurativa lesions, including a higher number of total lesions, sinus tracts, and abscesses. MRI's enhanced sensitivity to deeper and complex pathological changes provides a more comprehensive disease assessment, which critically informs treatment planning and preoperative evaluation. These findings support incorporating MRI into routine HS evaluation to improve disease staging accuracy and therapeutic outcomes, especially in patients with moderate to severe disease where management decisions are more complex.

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